

Mechanically robust hydrophobic fluorine-doped diamond-like carbon film on glass substrate

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ABSTRACT

Development of hydrophobic surfaces with a low friction coefficient is an impressive strategy for improving performance of self-cleaning glasses and photovoltaic cells. To this end, diamond-like carbon (DLC) films have been fabricated by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) by varying the fluorine concentration of the film. As fluorine is introduced to the DLC film, some fluorocarbon compounds, including CF and CF₂ and also CF₃, are formed as confirmed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). Additionally, the Raman spectroscopy analysis revealed a decrease in the sp³/sp² hybridization ratio of carbon atoms as the fluorine concentration increased in the DLC films. It is believed that the presence of fluorocarbon compounds on the surface and high surface roughness are the key factors responsible for the high hydrophobicity of the fluorine-doped DLC films. Nano-scratch and nanoindentation tests indicated a significant relationship between fluorine content and mechanical properties of the DLC films. The hardness and elastic modulus of the film were decreased by increasing the fluorine content of the film. With incorporation of fluorine (19.2 at.%) into the DLC film, the friction coefficient of 0.2 was obtained. The potential of the fluorine-doped DLC films with a moderate concentration of fluorine (19.2 at.%) was confirmed as a robust interface with adequate hydrophobicity for surface engineering of self-cleaning glasses.

1. Introduction

A growing need for hydrophobic surfaces in various applications such as self-cleaning windows [1], glass windshields [2], and photovoltaic cells [3,4] was reported. Therefore, a significant attention has been paid in recent years to the research and fabrication of robust hydrophobic coatings [5]. The hydrophobicity of materials with low surface free energy is improved more by rising the surface roughness, which has been emphasized in most published studies [6,7]. Although the improvement of hydrophobicity by increasing the surface roughness can be very effective for self-cleaning applications, it is not suitable for enhancing the performance in photovoltaic cells and glass windshields applications [8,9]. This is because it can increase the friction coefficient, which can complicate quick evacuation of water from the surface in harsh weather conditions. The glass surfaces then become more opaque, which might deteriorate the performance of photovoltaic cells and glass

windshields [10]. In other words, low friction force between water and the hydrophobic surface makes it easier for droplets to roll or slide along them and remove particles from surface than hydrophilic surface. As a result, it can increase the efficiency of self-cleaning significantly [11].

Only a limited number of studies deal with the fabrication of hydrophobic, low friction coefficient and wear resistant coatings on glass substrate. Agustín-Saenz et al. [12] fabricated an anti-reflective doubled-layer polyfluoroalkyl-silica coating on a glass substrate using sol-gel process. This coating shows high hydrophobicity and excellent wear resistance for the self-cleaning process. Maharjan et al. [13] introduced a hydrophobic nano-structured coating produced by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) of trichloro silane on a glass substrate. These self-cleaning coatings showed excellent abrasion resistance and superior nano-mechanical properties. The coatings also exhibited excellent wear resistance in corrosive environments, such as acid rain, alkali solution, and saline exposure. Wu et al. [14] utilized a mixture of

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trimethylmethoxysilane (TMMOS) and Ar in a microwave plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition technique to fabricate a robust hydrophobic coating on a glass substrate. To improve the hydrophobicity of the surface, they applied a post-treatment by CVD technique using a mixture of FAS-17 [(heptadecafluoro-1,1,2,2-tetrahydro-decyl)-1-trimethoxysilane] and trimethoxysilane (TMS). The contact angle of 150° was achieved for the coating, which showed a lower wear depth after nanoindentation test compared to the uncoated glass substrate. Vidal et al. [15] utilized an atmospheric jet plasma technic to fabricate a hydrophobic coating on a glass substrate. The mixture of aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) and perfluorohexene (PFH) was used as precursor to increase wear resistance and hydrophobicity of the coating. When APTES was used to fabricate the coatings, siloxane (SiOSi) typically forms. The high amount of SiOSi content in the coatings was responsible for having stable low friction coefficients and high adhesion strength, which was correlated with the fraction of APTES in precursor mixture. However, presence of perfluorohexene (PFH) could significantly reduce the surface free energy of the coating. Generally, presence of fluorocarbon groups is effective in improving surface hydrophobicity. For instance, polytetrafluoroethylene (Teflon) is effective for water-proof, nonsticking, and corrosion resistance applications [16]. However, Teflon does not possess suitable mechanical properties and wear resistance due to extreme viscoelastic deformation [17].

Diamond-like carbon (DLC) is a slightly hydrophobic coating which is excellent for wear resistant applications because of its high hardness and chemical inertness [18]. Nevertheless, with incorporation of fluorine into the diamond-like carbon (F-DLC) coating, the hydrophobicity of the coating can be improved [19]. S. Bhowmick et al. [20] deposited a F-DLC coating on M2 tool steel bar, increasing the water contact angle to 90° . They showed by atomistic simulation that fluorinated surfaces are hydrophobic because the C–F bonds are unable to create hydrogen bonding. Moreover, it is found that the hydrophobicity of the F-DLC coatings are more influenced by the CF_2 and CF_3 groups than by the CF group. In a different study, H. Ryu et al. [21] demonstrated that much more hydrophobicity could be achieved by depositing F-DLC coatings on microblasted Al606. It is due to the synergic influence of the high surface roughness and the hydrophobic nature of the F-DLC coating. Among the technologies which have been used to fabricate the F-DLC coating, the plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) is more popular than other methods, since the properties of the coating can be adjusted by changing the process parameters such as power, gas flow rate and chemical composition of the precursor. Moreover, it is versatile technology for scaling up the process for industrial applications from self-cleaning windows to solar cell components [22].

Several studies have been conducted to investigate how fluorine affects the hydrophobicity of carbon-based coating, [23], and some have emphasized tribological properties [24]. However, only a limited number of studies was conducted focusing on the effect of fluorine incorporation into DLC coatings on both hydrophobic and tribological properties. To the best of our knowledge, the application of F-DLC film on glass substrate for the development of hydrophobicity and friction reduction has never been reported, which has a direct impact on the full capacity of the solar panel and self-cleaning glasses. High hydrophobicity without creating a rough structure on the substrate is another novel aspect of this work that will make these coated glasses an excellent choice for industrial scale manufacturing of glasses for self-cleaning and solar cell applications. Here, the main objective of this study is to find a balance between friction reduction and hydrophobicity of the F-DLC films on glass substrate. To this end, the role of fluorine was studied in the structural evolution of the DLC films fabricated using the PECVD method on glass substrate. Moreover, influence of fluorine incorporation in DLC film on nano-mechanical and tribological properties, as well as the hydrophobicity of the film are evaluated.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Film preparation

The glass microscope slides utilized as substrate were 1 mm thick, with a dimension of $25\text{ mm} \times 75\text{ mm}$. A PECVD technique (Oxford Instruments Plasma Technology, PlasmaPro 80) was utilized to deposit DLC film containing different fluorine concentrations which its Schematic diagram shown in Fig. 1. Before deposition, the specimens were sonicated for 5 min in acetone and then 5 min in ethanol for cleaning. Afterwards, the cleaned samples were placed inside the plasma chamber and were then treated with an argon cleaning process for 5 min with a flow rate of 100 standard cubic centimeters per minute (sccm). The argon plasma cleaning was carried out at a work pressure of 13.3 Pa, RF plasma (13.56 MHz) and a power of 75 W. Various CHF_3/CH_4 flow ratios of 0, 0.25, 0.5, and 1 at a working pressure of 53.3 Pa were used to deposit the fluorine-doped DLC films. All films were deposited at 60°C (external heater) with a power of 50 W and RF plasma of 13.56 MHz. During the process, the working pressure was controlled by an automatic pressure controller (APC).

2.2. Film characterization

The Raman spectroscopy (Raman Microscope Renishaw inVia-Reflex) was used to evaluate the structural variations of the films. The spectra were recorded using a laser with the wavelength of 532 nm and power of 7.5 W in the wavenumber range of 1200 to 1800 cm^{-1} . All Raman spectra were fitted to two peaks of G at 1560 cm^{-1} and D at 1360 cm^{-1} . To compare the structural variations, the position of the G peak and the intensity ratio of D and G peaks (I_D/I_G) were calculated. Moreover, the hydrogen content in the amorphous carbon structure can be estimated by Eq. (1) [25]:

$$H (\%) = 21.7 + 16.6 \times \log [m/I(G) (\mu\text{m})] \quad (1)$$

where I_G and m are the intensity of the normalized G peak and the

Fig. 1. Diagram schematically illustrating the configuration of the PECVD system for depositing DLC films with various fluorine concentrations.

intensity of the photoluminescence (PL) of Raman spectra, respectively. The intensity of the photoluminescence of the Raman spectra was calculated from the slope of the raw spectra baseline between 1000 cm^{-1} and 1800 cm^{-1} of the Raman shift range.

The surface chemistry of the films was analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). The Kratos Axis Supra apparatus (Manchester, UK) was employed; it consisted of a hybrid lens model, a monochromatic Al K X-ray source, and a 15 mA emission current. To record the survey spectra, the measurement with the pass energy of 80 eV and the scanning step of 0.5 eV was performed. A pass energy of 15 eV with the scanning steps of 0.05 eV were applied to record the high-resolution spectra. The atomic concentration of elements was calculated by Casa XPS software (version 2.3.22). To calibrate the peaks, the C1s emission with a binding energy of 285 eV was selected as the reference peak. The linear background method was adopted, and the Gaussian/Lorentzian line shape was employed for all fitted peaks to calculate the atomic concentration of different carbon bonds.

A high-resolution scanning electron microscope (HR-SEM) FEI Verios 460L (VERIOS) was employed to examine the fracture surface of the film deposited on the glass substrate. The topography and surface roughness of the specimens were studied with atomic force microscopy (BRUKER, Innova Microscope). A See System E Advex Instruments (SEESYSTEM) were used to measure the contact angles of the films and glass substrate using water and diiodomethane as wetting liquids. Based on the Owens–Wendt model, the dispersive and polar energy of the surfaces were calculated, facilitating the determination of the total surface free energy as shown by the following Eq. (2) [26]:

$$\gamma_l (1 + \cos \Theta) = 2 \left[(\gamma_s^d \gamma_l^d)^{1/2} + (\gamma_s^p \gamma_l^p)^{1/2} \right] \quad (2)$$

where the superscript letters p and d stand for the polar and dispersive components, respectively. Θ stands for the contact angle and γ is for surface free energy. For the water, 51 mJ/m^2 and 21.8 mJ/m^2 are the corresponding values for the γ_l^p and γ_l^d . Regarding the diiodomethane, the values of 0.38 mJ/m^2 and 50.42 mJ/m^2 were used for γ_l^p and γ_l^d , respectively.

To measure the elastic modulus and hardness of the F-DLC films, a nanoindenter (Hysitron TI 950) equipped with a calibrated diamond tip with Berkovich geometry was used. The nano-mechanical properties were calculated according to the Oliver–Pharr method. In order to minimize the influence of the substrate on the results, the indentation depth for all films was set to <10 % of the film thickness. At least nine measurements at a maximum load of 500 μN were performed on each sample for better certainty. To determine the films' adhesion to the substrate, a nano-scratch test was performed by a scratch tester equipped with a conical diamond tip. A progressive loading mode with a rate of 200 $\mu\text{N}/\text{s}$ and a peak load at 4000 μN , and a sliding speed of 600 nm/s was set for all tests. In addition, a constant load of 500 μN at a sliding distance of 10 μm for 60 s was applied to assess the friction coefficient of the films. To measure the mechanical and tribological properties, the coatings with the same thickness were used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fracture surface and morphology

The fracture surface of the F-DLC film deposited on glass substrate is shown in Fig. 2. The film thickness was measured \sim 500 nm and the film adhered to the glass substrate adequately. Generally, DLC film grows as a result of competition between etching and deposition. The deposition rate decreased from 21 $\text{nm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for pure DLC film to 15 $\text{nm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for the F-DLC coating with CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate of 1. This has been explained by a rise in the density of $-\text{CF}_x$ groups and F^+ in the plasma. Due to a lower sticking coefficient and more surface etching, it can reduce deposition rate [27].

Fig. 3 shows the AFM images of the surface morphology of the F-DLC

Fig. 2. SEM fracture surface image of the F-DLC film deposited on the glass substrate.

films deposited with different CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate ratios. There are no obvious defects on any of the as-deposited films. However, by increasing the CHF_3/CH_4 flow ratio from 0 to 1, the root-mean-square roughness (RMS) of the F-DLC film increased from 0.5 nm to 1.4 nm. The surface typically has more roughness when the growing layer is etched by atomic hydrogen because of a higher bombardment. The amount of $-\text{CF}_x$ groups and F^+ in the plasma atmosphere grew as the CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate ratio increased in the chamber. The F^+ is known as an efficient etching agent but as the amount of $-\text{CF}_x$ groups increased, self-bias voltage reduced, leading to a decrease in the ions' kinetic energy [24]. This low amount of ions energy is not sufficient to remove certain asperities and consequently higher surface roughness can be achieved [28].

3.2. Surface chemistry of the films

The effect of CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate ratio on the surface chemistry and structure of the films was investigated by XPS and Raman spectroscopy. Fig. 4a shows the elemental compositions of the F-DLC films in different CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate ratios obtained from the XPS survey spectra. Although there was no oxygen in the precursors, the atomic concentration of oxygen remained constant around 9 % for all the films. The presence of oxygen in the film is attributed to the surface reactions of the film with oxygen in the atmosphere after deposition. Moreover, autoxidation is an inevitable reaction which occurs in some monomers such as thiophene [29] and trichloroethane [30] used as precursors. As shown in Fig. 4a, by importing the CHF_3 in the chamber up to the CHF_3/CH_4 ratio of 0.25, the fluorine concentration increased to 11.8 at.%, whereas the concentration of carbon decreased from 91.8 at.% to 81.1 at.%. When CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate ratio rose from 0.5 to 1, the fluorine concentration grew considerably from 19.2 at.% to 28.1 at.%. The increase in fluorine content of the F-DLC films is the result of a higher content of fluorinated components in the plasma atmosphere. To obtain more details about the chemical bindings of fluorine and carbon, the high-resolution spectra of C1s were deconvoluted (Fig. 4b). The C1s spectra were decomposed into five partial peaks centered at 284.9, 286.9, 287.8, 289, 291, and 293 eV, which corresponded to C–C/C–H, C–O, C=O, C–F, CF_2 and CF_3 bonds, respectively [31–34]. Although the CF_3 bonds were not observed in the F-DLC with the low and moderate CHF_3/CH_4 ratio in the flow, they appeared in the sample with the highest CHF_3/CH_4 ratio. With an increase of the CHF_3/CH_4 ratio from 0.5 to 1, the concentration of the CF_2 increased from 6.3 at.% to 8.2 at.%, and CF_3 with the concentration of 16.3 at.% were formed (Fig. 4c). As the films' fluorine concentration increases, more carbon atoms tend to bond with fluorine atoms, hence a gradual conversion from C–C bonds to fluorocarbon groups such as CF_2 and CF_3 can be observed.

Fig. 3. AFM surface morphology of the F-DLC films with various CHF_3/CH_4 flow rate ratios of (a) 0 (b) 0.25 (c) 0.5 (d) 1.

Along with XPS, one of the indirect approaches to determine the bonding types of carbon materials is Raman spectroscopy. In general, two important peaks of G ($\sim 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and D ($\sim 1360\text{ cm}^{-1}$) can be deconvoluted in Raman spectra of the DLC films [19,35–38]. The D peak arises from the disordering of sp^2 carbon atoms in aromatic rings, while the G peak is allocated to the stretching of carbon-carbon bonds in aromatic rings and olefinic chains [18,39]. The Raman spectra of the DLC and F-DLC films are shown in Fig. 5a–d, deconvoluted into two Gaussian peaks of D and G. By introducing fluorine (11.8 at.%) into the DLC film, the G peak position increased to 1529 cm^{-1} and the I_D/I_G increased to 0.25 (Fig. 5e, b).

As the concentration of fluorine increased from 19.2 at.% to 28.1 at.%, the G peak positions shifted from 1538 cm^{-1} to 1549 cm^{-1} , and the I_D/I_G ratio rose from 0.33 to 0.49. This behavior indicates the decrease of the sp^3/sp^2 ratio with the increasing fluorine content, and the graphitization is more pronounced. Moreover, fluorine can reduce the cross-linking of the carbon network by collapsing the sp^3 structure [40]. Therefore, as fluorine atoms are incorporated to the DLC film, a film with lower density and lower compressive stress can be achieved. The highly electronegative fluorine atoms are able to create a single bond only with carbon. Therefore, the C–F bonds that were formed can stick out of the carbon network due to the difficulty to form longer chains and rings [24,41]. The hydrogen content of the films was estimated using Eq.1. By adding up to 11.8 at.% fluorine, the hydrogen content of the DLC film increased from 22.8 at.% to 23.2 at.%. Furthermore, the hydrogen content increased from 25.2 at.% to 26.4 at.% as the fluorine concentration rose from 19.2 at.% to 28.1 at.%. Due to the high electronegativity of the fluorine atoms, hydrogen bonds are formed between the fluorine-containing groups with hydrogen-containing groups and free hydrogen [42]. Slightly increasing the intensity of the photoluminescence (PL) of the F-DLC film as fluorine concentration increased, can be assisted to a polymer-like structural arrangement in the film [43]. It can indicate a decrease in the compressive stress of the F-film by

increasing the fluorine content [44], which is consistent with other Raman results.

3.3. Wettability

Surface hydrophobicity significantly affects the performance of glass for self-cleaning applications. Therefore, surface free energy (SFE) is an essential factor when determining the hydrophobicity of coated glasses. To calculate the SFE of the samples, two liquids with significant polarity differences were used. For this purpose, water and diiodomethane were chosen as polar and non-polar liquids, respectively to measure the contact angle of the films and the substrate. The water contact angle of the glass substrate was $\sim 9^\circ$, whereas its diiodomethane contact angle was only $\sim 1^\circ$ which was impractical to show (Fig. 6a). By introducing fluorine (11.8 at.%) to the DLC films, the water and diiodomethane contact angles increased sharply to 81° and 36° , respectively. With further increase of the fluorine content up to 28.1 at.%, the contact angles of water and diiodomethane reached 105° and 59° , respectively. The surface free energy of the film and its dispersive and polar components were calculated using the Owens-Wendt model [26,45]. As can be seen in Fig. 6b, by incorporating fluorine content (11.8 at.%) into the DLC film, the total surface free energy decreased from $54.7\text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ to $45.6\text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. Both components of the SFE followed the same trend as total SFE when the fluorine concentration in the DLC films was increased. As the fluorine concentration rose from 11.8 at.% to 28.1 at.%, the polar energy decreased from $3.87\text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ to $0.1\text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ and the dispersive energy decreased from $41.7\text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ to $18.06\text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$. The data show the hydrophobicity of the F-DLC films improved significantly as the fluorine content of the DLC films increased.

Such increase in hydrophobicity in F-DLC films is related to the presence of the CF_3 and CF_2 groups on the surface of the F-DLC films with fluorine concentration of 19.2 at.% and 28.1 at.%, as confirmed by XPS in Section 3.2. In other words, higher concentration of the less polar

Fig. 4. a) Chemical composition of the F-DLC films with various CHF₃/CH₄ flow rate ratios obtained by XPS survey spectra b) Normalized XPS C1s high-resolution spectra of the F-DLC films fitted by different components c) The atomic concentration of the deconvoluted peaks from C1 high-resolution spectra for different CHF₃/CH₄ flow rate ratios.

groups of CF₂ and CF₃ [46] on the surface can reduce the SFE of the F-DLC film with high fluorine concentration. Because of the high electronegativity of fluorine atoms, strong bonds were formed between carbon and fluorine. The cleavage of such strong bonds is thermodynamically difficult [47,48]. Surface topography is another critical factor for controlling wettability behavior. Based on the wettability theory, as

the surface roughness increases, a droplet tends to reduce its contact area to the surface to lessen its SFE [49]. As indicated by AFM, the surface roughness increased by increasing the fluorine concentration, which was also associated with the increase in surface hydrophobicity. Low surface free energy films have a lower wet area than high surface free energy films due to the reduced force keeping the water in contact

Fig. 5. The Raman spectra of the F-DLC films deconvoluted into two Gaussian peaks of D and G with fluorine atomic concentration of a) 0 at.% b) 11.8 at.% c) 19.2 at.% d) 28.2 at.% e) The variation of Raman parameters of the G peak position and the I_D/I_G ratio versus fluorine atomic concentration.

with the surface [50,51]. Therefore, the dust particles or any surface contamination are carried away over time by the water droplet on the F-DLC films as it rolls over the surface with high concentration of CF_2 and CF_3 .

3.4. Mechanical properties

To find a correlation between the structural evolution and mechanical properties of the F-DLC films, nanoindentation tests were conducted on all samples.

Fig. 7a shows that DLC film without fluorine initially exhibited a

Fig. 6. a) Water and diiodomethane contact angles of the glass substrate and the F-DLC films as a function of fluorine atomic concentration. b) The dispersive, polar surface energy, and total surface free energy of the glass substrate, DLC, and F-DLC films.

hardness of 13.1 GPa while it was gradually reduced from 13.1 GPa to 10.9 GPa by incorporating fluorine (11.8 at.%). With a further increase of the fluorine content up to 28.1 at.%, the hardness decreased to 8.1 GPa. Similar behavior was also observed for the elastic modulus of the films (Fig. 7b). As the fluorine concentration increased from 11.8 at.% to 28.1 at.%, the elastic modulus was reduced from 103.7 GPa to 85.1 GPa.

The decreasing trend in the hardness and elastic modulus might be attributed to sp^3/sp^2 hybridized carbon in DLC film. As shown by Raman spectroscopy results, increasing fluorine concentration cause a decrease in the fraction of sp^3 hybridized carbon in the DLC films. By incorporating the fluorine atoms into the DLC film, cross-links between C—C networks can be broken, yielding lower compressive stress and more open structure [24,27]. As a result, both the hardness and elastic modulus showed a downward trend with the increasing the fluorine concentration into the DLC film.

The H/E parameter related to the elastic strain of the film to failure associated with fracture toughness was introduced to predict the tribological behavior of the film [52]. Fig. 7 shows the H/E ratio of the DLC films in various fluorine concentration. The highest H/E = 0.11 was obtained for the DLC film without the incorporation of fluorine. By increasing fluorine content up to 11.8 at.%, the H/E was reduced to 0.106 and remained unchanged also for the coating containing 19.2 at.% of fluorine. However, when it reached 28.1 at.%, the H/E ratio sharply decreased to <0.1. Understanding the fracture mechanism of the film is significantly impacted by such changes in the H/E of the F-DLC films. It is known that the films with H/E > 0.1 if they show high elastic recovery and void-free structure, can be considered fracture resistant [53]. Therefore, the DLC films with low fluorine content, until some critical concentration (19.2 at.%), can exhibit good tribological behavior.

3.5. Nano scratch test

To further study the effect of the fluorine content on nano-mechanical behavior of the DLC films, nano-scratch tests with a progressive loading regime were carried out on the samples. Fig. 8 shows the evolution of lateral and normal forces with scratch distance. The minimum normal force at which the initial film damage from the glass substrate occurred is assigned as 'critical load' (CL).

The delamination of the DLC film took place at a scratch distance of 4.06 μm (CL = 1590 μN), whereas the addition of fluorine to DLC film up to 11.8 at.% increased the critical load for delamination to 2290 μN and scratch length to 5.84 μm (Fig. 8).

With a further increase of the fluorine concentration (28.1 at.%), the critical load was reduced (CL = 1410 μN) and the delamination of the film occurred at a lower scratch length (3.62 μm) compared to other

films. The highest critical load was obtained for the F-DLC (19.2 at.% F) which was strongly related to a lower internal stress and a more favorable H/E ratio, as shown in Section 3.4. In other words, when fluorine concentration of the F-DLC film rose, the sp^3/sp^2 ratio decreased, and the cross-links between C—C networks were reduced. Moreover, the bonds in sp^2 -hybridized carbon are shorter than in sp^3 -hybridized carbon, leading to a decreasing strain in the DLC films [54,55].

All the factors mentioned above contribute to a decrease of the internal stress in the film and, consequently, facilitate adequate film adhesion to the substrate as a result of fluorine incorporation into the DLC structure. However, due to the lower hardness of the F-DLC film with high fluorine concentration (28.2 at.%), the stylus quickly reached the substrate, leading to easier film delamination.

To develop a reliable self-cleaning surface with low surface energy, it is essential to ensure a low coefficient of friction in the films. Fig. 9 shows the friction coefficient curves of the films and glass substrate versus sliding time under ambient air obtained by micro-scratch tester. Regardless of the film deposition conditions, all friction coefficients of the coated glasses are lower than the friction coefficient of the uncoated glass (approximately 0.7). By applying the DLC film on the glass substrate, the friction coefficient decreased sharply to around 0.24. By introducing fluorine (11.8 at.%) into the DLC film, the friction coefficient decreased to ~0.2. As the fluorine concentration increased to 19.2 at.%, the friction coefficient did not change considerably compared to the F-DLC film with 11.8 at.% of fluorine. With a further increase of fluorine concentration up to 28.1 at.%, the friction curve fluctuated more, and the friction coefficient increased to nearly 0.3.

Generally, the presence of dangling carbon bonds with hydrogen on the surface of the hydrogenated DLC films can make the surface passive, hence, reducing adhesive interactions in tribological contacts. This can play a key role in reducing the friction coefficient and stabilizing the frictional behavior of the DLC films [56,57]. However, by doping the fluorine atoms into the amorphous structure of the DLC, some hydrogen atoms are replaced by fluorine (C—F bonds are more robust than the C—H bonds). The fluorocarbon bonds in F-DLC film, such as CF_2 and CF_3 , generate stronger interface repulsion forces and hinder the adhesive interaction on the counter surfaces more effectively than carbon bonds with the hydrogen in the DLC film (Fluorine-free).

However, as demonstrated in Section 3.4, further increase of the fluorine concentration up to 28.1 at.% decreased the H/E ratio of the film to <0.1, making them unsuitable for tribological applications [52]. Moreover, due to the higher amount of precursors in the plasma atmosphere during the F-DLC (28.1 at.% F) deposition, the surface roughness increased sharply compared to other F-DLC films with a lower fluorine concentration. Despite higher fluorocarbon compounds content in F-

Fig. 7. Nano-mechanical properties of the F-DLC films versus fluorine atomic concentration.

Fig. 8. Nano scratch test results including the lateral and normal forces versus scratch distance for F-DLC films with different fluorine atomic concentration of a) 0 at.% b) 11.8 at.% c) 19.2 at.% d) 28.2 at.%.

Fig. 9. Friction coefficient curves of the glass, DLC, and F-DLC films with various fluorine content versus sliding time under ambient air obtained by nanoindentation test.

DLC with 28.1 at.%, compared to other films that consequently led to a stronger repulsion force on the surface, its properties, such as high surface roughness and low H/E, can increase the friction coefficient and hence impair the tribological properties considerably.

Finding an appropriate balance between mechanical and hydrophobic properties for F-DLC coating is still a challenging issue. X. Wei et al. [58] observed that while doping fluorine into the DLC coating can increase its water contact angle by 79° , the coating shows poor bearing capacity, therefore silicon as a co dopant was applied to improve it. In another study, J. Wang et al. [41] indicated that the friction coefficient of the carbon-based coating can be decreased to <0.1 by doping fluorine up to 4.8 at.%, but they achieved a water contact angle of 77.4° indicating the insufficient hydrophobicity. However, F-DLC film (19.2 at.% F) exhibited the best combination of tribological properties and surface hydrophobicity in the current study, making it a promising candidate for self-cleaning glasses and photovoltaic cell applications.

4. Conclusion

Fluorine-doped diamond-like carbon (F-DLC) films were deposited on a glass substrate using plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) technique with a mixture of CHF_3 and CH_4 as precursors. Fluorine was incorporated into the DLC films, creating CF and CF_2 bonds with carbon atoms. CF_3 groups were also identified by XPS at high fluorine concentrations. The results of Raman spectroscopy indicated

that the ratio of sp^3/sp^2 hybridized carbon decreased with increasing fluorine content, promoting the graphitization of the film. The surface hydrophobicity increased due to the presence of the CF_3 and CF_2 groups on the film surface. It was found that increasing the CHF_3/CH_4 flow ratio can significantly increase surface roughness of the F-DLC film. Indentation elastic modulus and hardness of the films decreased by increasing the fluorine content of the F-DLC films due to the reduction of the content of sp^3 hybridized carbon. The highest critical load required for coating delamination from the glass substrate was achieved for the F-DLC film with moderate fluorine concentration (19.2 at.%). This result was correlated with the lower internal stress and appropriate H/E ratio. The F-DLC film with 19.2 at.% showed the lowest friction coefficient due to the favorable H/E ratio and the presence of hydrophobic fluorocarbon compounds, which can eliminate adhesive interactions with the counter surfaces. The F-DLC film (28.1 at.% F) showed high friction coefficient and poor film adhesion to the substrate compared to other films, due to the increased surface roughness and low mechanical properties. The combination of surface hydrophobicity, nanomechanical properties, and frictional behavior make the F-DLC film with moderate fluorine content (19.2 at.%) an excellent option for the next generation of self-cleaning glasses and photovoltaic cells.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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